

The Impact of Selected Economic Indicators for the Development of Zlin Region in the Czech Republic

D. Charvatova, Z. Charvat

Abstract—This article considers with the influence of selected economic indicators for the development of the Zlin region. Development of the region is mainly influenced by business entities which are located in the region, as well as investors who contribute to the development of regions. For the development of the region it is necessary for skilled workers remain in the region and not to leave these skilled workers. The above-mentioned and other factors are affecting the development of each region.

Keyword—Macroeconomic indicators, population, the overall increase in population, location and area, territory, Zlin Region.

I. INTRODUCTION

DISTRICTS that make up the currently Zlin region, have been in the past, before 1989, and also at the beginning of the transformation processes after 1989, traditionally seen as economically strong areas with large industrial plants. Trouble began to appear in the first wave of privatization. These problems were mainly caused by external influences such as the method of privatization of large enterprises in the Czech Republic, poor transport services and access to the region on these issues as well, among other things involved the distribution of the Republic, and others. The emerging small and medium-sized enterprises in these could not be able to replace the large industrial enterprises with a wide range of backgrounds, which have been in the past. Therefore, this work will address the analysis of selected economic and social factors Zlin region, affecting its development.

II. GOALS AND METHODOLOGY

The aim of this work is to analyze the economic and social factors Zlin region and its comparison in the Czech Republic. Sub-goals of this work is a comparison of past and current developments and to propose recommendations to improve the status quo.

The work will be based on an analysis of secondary data sources document modification

III. LOCATION AND SIZE

Zlin region was established on 1 January 2000 on the basis of the Constitutional Act No. 347 of 3 December 1997 on the creation of senior local government units. It was created by merging districts Zlin, Kromeriz, and Buenos Aires, which

belonged to the Southern Moravian region, a district of Vsetin, which fell within the Czech Republic. Along with the Olomouc region consists of cohesion South Moravia. With effect from 1 1st 2003 established 13 administrative districts of municipalities with extended powers (the village III. Instance), in which it operates 25 regional districts in charge of municipalities (municipalities II. Instance). [1]

Located on East Republic, where the eastern edge of the border with Slovakia, in the southwest region bordering Jihomoravským, in the north - west with Olomouc in the northern part of the Moravian-Silesian region. Its size 3 964 km² is the fourth smallest in the region of the country. It has a total of 304 municipalities (of which 30 cities), in which at the end of 2006 lived 589 839 inhabitants. Population density 149 obyvatel/km² significantly exceeds the national average.

The population density is the highest in the district of Zlín (187 inhabitants/km²) and the lowest in the district of Vsetin (127 inhabitants/km²). [1]

PICTURE 1
LOCATION OF ZLIN REGION IN THE CZECH REPUBLIC

IV. POPULATION

The total population of the Zlin region since 1994 has reduced. In 2006, 589 839 inhabitants lived in the territory of Zlin region. An increasing proportion of the population in poproduktivním age characterizes the development of age composition of the population, the year 2005, the proportion of people over 64 years increased from 14.6% to 14.9%. Nevertheless, the age structure in economic terms is still

favorable. Average age Zlín region in 2006 was 40.2 years. [1]

CHART I
THE AGE COMPOSITION OF THE POPULATION IN ZLÍN REGION ACCORDING TO POPULATION PROJECTIONS

Source: [2]

V. ECONOMIC DATA

Economy in the region was and is based mainly on the exploitation of raw materials and semi-finished products. Export in the region is adversely affected by the position of the region in the Czech Republic. The gross domestic product, the Zlín region ranks the 9th among the region in the Czech Republic. In 2006, GDP reached an average value of 1 inhabitant region 254 466 CZK at current prices. Industrial potential Zlín region consists of companies manufacturing industry, which is 17.6% of the total registered entities. In particular, the business metalworking industry, wood, electronics and textiles. Their distinctive aspect is, however, the low level of modernization of production in comparison with the Czech Republic. In agriculture, there was the year 2005 to reduce the average Yields per acre by 0.5 tonnes to 4.6 tonnes average annual milk yield per cow is to 1 compared with last year increased by 152 l, when was 6 893 l.

The housing construction was completed during 2006 on the territory of the Region 1 138 flats, of which 624 family houses. The average living area completed home was 74.9 m².

At the end of the year remained deployed 8 354 flats. At 31 12th 2006 registered the Czech Statistical Office in the Zlín region total 130 477 legal and physical entities, of which 15 475 bodies had staff, which is 5.5% more than the same date 2005. With the number of employees 25 and more is in the region 1 586 companies.

The number of employed in the national economy in 2006 against the previous year increased by 11.3 thousand. people. As can be seen in the following tables 3 and the average gross monthly wage of employees in 2006 was 17 387, - CZK, which is below the national average (20 207, - EUR).

TABLE I
AVERAGE MONTHLY GROSS WAGES OF EMPLOYEES

NAME OF NUTS	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006
Czech republic	13 48	14 63	15 85	16 92	17 03	19 02	20 20
Capital city Prague	4	3	7	0	0	4	7
Středočeský region	18 86	20 80	19 89	21 09	22 93	23 93	25 28
Jihočeský region	5	0	7	3	5	3	1
Plzeňský region	13 42	14 40	15 53	16 56	16 63	18 63	19 81
Karlovarský region	9	7	4	8	9	4	2
Ústecký region	12 55	13 52	14 02	14 88	15 49	16 63	17 73
Liberecký region	1	8	9	1	9	2	2
Královéhradecký region	12 82	13 97	14 84	15 82	16 28	17 62	18 73
Pardubický region	9	7	0	1	1	7	1
Vysočina	12 11	13 04	13 53	14 47	14 92	16 00	16 99
Jihomoravský region	9	2	5	2	6	2	8
Olomoucký region	12 64	13 55	14 26	15 31	15 82	17 09	18 09
Moravskoslezský region	6	3	9	3	3	4	7
Zlín region	12 43	13 46	14 08	15 10	15 28	17 00	18 12
Moravskoslezský region	5	3	1	6	3	8	0
Středočeský region	12 31	13 18	13 75	14 75	15 48	16 37	17 31
Jihočeský region	2	3	3	2	3	1	3
Středočeský region	11 91	12 86	13 53	14 58	15 24	16 35	17 26
Středočeský region	7	8	9	1	8	7	9
Středočeský region	11 72	12 84	13 44	14 49	15 07	16 29	17 62
Středočeský region	1	8	1	1	2	4	2
Středočeský region	12 53	13 61	14 05	15 19	16 04	16 98	18 35
Středočeský region	4	9	9	3	8	4	6
Středočeský region	11 89	12 80	13 37	14 30	15 21	16 19	17 08
Středočeský region	2	0	3	4	5	3	7
Zlín region	12 11	13 14	13 84	14 69	15 10	16 42	17 38
Zlín region	4	8	3	3	2	0	7
Moravskoslezský region	12 96	14 04	14 92	15 83	16 18	17 61	18 69
Moravskoslezský region	6	9	3	7	8	8	0

Source: [11]

Registered unemployment rate

Registered unemployment rate reflects the proportion of the number of unemployed registered by employment offices on the available labor force (in percent), where the numerator and denominator are designed in accordance with the characteristics of the algorithms. [11]

TABLE II
REGISTERED UNEMPLOYMENT RATE IN %

NAME OF NUTS	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007
Czech republic	8,90	9,81	10,31	9,47	8,90	7,67	5,98
Capital city Prague	3,39	3,73	4,02	3,58	3,20	2,72	2,16
Středočeský region	6,76	7,21	7,43	6,85	6,30	5,32	4,25
Jihočeský region	6,03	6,65	6,96	6,59	6,70	5,68	4,47

Plzeňský region	6,52	7,06	7,60	6,74	6,40	5,60	4,43
Karlovarský region	8,71	10,07	10,62	10,75	10,30	9,20	7,32
Ústecký region	15,83	17,13	17,94	15,85	15,40	13,77	10,96
Liberecký region	7,35	8,68	9,48	8,22	7,70	7,04	6,05
Královéhradecký region	6,30	7,30	7,89	7,67	7,30	6,32	4,71
Pardubický region	7,93	8,66	9,42	8,94	8,30	6,91	5,43
Vysočina	7,02	8,32	9,20	8,85	8,20	7,10	5,63
Jihomoravský region	9,73	11,20	11,45	10,69	10,20	8,82	6,92
Olomoucký region	11,78	12,20	12,48	11,73	10,60	8,97	6,73
Zlín region	8,51	10,22	10,61	9,53	9,30	7,75	6,02
Moravskoslezský region	15,11	15,89	16,84	15,66	14,20	12,58	9,62

Source: [11]

At 31 12th 2006 registration offices work Zlín region a total of 25 601 job seekers registered unemployment rate was 7.8%. As part of the region it had the highest unemployment rate district Vsetín (9.7%) and on the other hand, the lowest district Zlín (6.3%). [1]

In 2007, registered unemployment was 6.02% in the Zlín region. In the tab. No.4 can see that compared to 2006, the registered unemployment in 2007 in the Zlín region decreased by 1.73%. Over the years 2001 - 2007, the registered unemployment in the Zlín region in 2007, the lowest.

Compared with the average rate of registered unemployment, the Czech Republic and the Zlín region in 2007, was registered unemployment in the Zlín region of 0.04% higher than the national average.

The number of economically active per 100 inhabitants

This indicator reflects the economically active population, which includes all fifteen-year-old and older, which belongs to the category of labor that is classified as persons employed or unemployed. [11]

NAME OF NUTS	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006
Czech republic	50,42	50,37	50,26	50,22	50,47	50,54
Capital city Prague	54,47	54,32	54,44	53,44	53,95	54,30
Středočeský region	50,54	51,07	50,78	50,56	50,16	50,42
Jihočeský region	50,79	50,30	50,05	50,28	50,43	50,65
Plzeňský region	51,36	51,13	50,55	50,87	51,53	50,80
Karlovarský region	52,55	51,80	51,57	51,74	53,24	52,26
Ústecký region	50,88	50,03	49,45	50,92	50,88	51,11
Liberecký region	50,47	50,48	50,17	51,03	50,25	49,98
Královéhradecký region	50,53	50,20	49,93	49,10	49,20	50,45
Pardubický region	48,96	49,67	49,95	48,94	49,29	49,49
Vysočina	49,16	48,82	48,54	49,39	49,71	49,55
Jihomoravský region	49,39	49,12	49,32	49,45	49,46	49,47
Olomoucký region	48,87	49,83	49,68	49,22	49,16	49,74
Zlín region	48,83	48,22	49,10	48,89	49,14	49,96
Moravskoslezský region	48,68	49,02	48,80	48,64	49,73	48,83

Source: [11]

In 2006, in Zlín region number of economically active people increased over 2005 of 0.82 persons. In comparison Zlín region with an average of the Czech Republic, the

number of economically active persons in the Zlín region lower on the 0.58 persons in 2006.

TABLE IV
BASIC ECONOMIC DATA ZLÍN REGION IN 2006

Index	Unit of measure	Zlín region	CZ
The share of the Region's on production of GDP	%	4,6	100,0
GDP on inhabitant in PPS	%	64,1	75,6
Registered unemployment rate	%	7,8	7,7
The number of applicants for employment for the 1 free working station		5,0	4,8
The number of registered organizations per 1000 inhabitants		221,2	236,3
Length of roads and motorways to 10 000	km	36,0	54,0
Status of direct foreigner investment per 1 000	mil. czech crown	50,0	162,0

Source: [8]

Table No.IV are selected economic data characterizing the position of Zlín region in 2006 throughout the Republic.

The share of the region's GDP in the Czech Republic

Gross domestic product is a key indicator of the development of the economy. Represents the sum of value added processing in all sectors in activities deemed in the national accounts as a productive (ie, including market and non-market nature). [9]

TABLE IV
THE SHARE OF THE REGION'S GDP IN THE CZECH REPUBLIC

NAME OF NUTS	2003	2004	2005	2006
Czech republic	100	100	100	100
Capital city Prague	23,9	23,9	24	24,3
Středočeský region	10,5	10,4	10,4	10,3
Jihočeský region	5,5	5,5	5,5	5,5
Plzeňský region	5	5,2	5,2	5
Karlovarský region	2,4	2,3	2,3	2,3
Ústecký region	6,6	6,6	6,5	6,5
Liberecký region	3,4	3,3	3,3	3,5
Královéhradecký region	4,8	4,8	4,8	4,6
Pardubický region	4,2	4,1	4,1	4
Vysočina	4,3	4,2	4,2	4,2
Jihomoravský region	10,3	10,2	10,2	10
Olomoucký region	4,8	4,9	4,9	4,6
Zlín region	4,8	4,6	4,6	4,6
Moravskoslezský region	9,6	10	10	10,5

Source: [10]

Zlín region in 2006 contributed to the formation of GDP

4.6%. Over the years 2004 - 2006, the share of GDP did not, it was constant. Only in 2003, the Zlin region involved in the formation of GDP 4.8%, which was 0.02% more than in other years.

As can be seen from the following chart III, in 2006, the most in the creation of GDP Prague contributed to 24.3%, the Moravia-Silesia region and to 10.5% and 10.3% Central region. Zlin region is among the countries that have lower levels of formation of GDP than the national average.

CHART II
THE SHARE OF THE REGION'S ON PRODUCTION OF GDP IN THE CZECH REPUBLIC IN %

The net disposable income of households per 1 inhabitant in %

Net disposable income of households is the amount you can pay the household final consumption, savings and financial assets in the accumulation of tangible and intangible assets.

Shows how the balance of primary income placed znovurozdělením: normal taxes, social contributions and benefits and other current transfers. Indicator us to a large extent indicates the level of material wealth of households permanently residing in different regions. [10]

CHART III
THE SHARE OF NET DISPOSABLE INCOME OF HOUSEHOLDS PER 1 INHABITANT IN %

The share of net disposable income of households 1 inhabitant in the Zlin region in 2006 was 5.4%. In comparison Zlin region to other regions in the Czech Republic, the proportion of net disposable income of households 1 inhabitant belonged to lower, it shows chart no 3rd.

VI. CONCLUSION

Analysis of selected economic and social indicators, it was found that the Zlin region involved in the production of substandard GDP substandard compared with other regions in the Czech Republic. By the analysis was found that Zlin region in comparison with other regions has a higher rate of registered unemployment.

Even though Zlin region should be adaptable workforce These effects could not be overcome despite the fact that in the Zlin region, there is significant potential for internal region in the form of zručné and adaptable workforce with an active attitude towards economic mainstay.

Other factors that negatively affect the development of the Zlin region are poor transport availability, which is caused by a marginal geographical location Zlin region, low Zlin region attractive for investors, low attractiveness for skilled workers, small businessmen interested in the business in this region. The result of all these factors is below the creation of GDP Zlin region in comparison with other regions in the Czech Republic.

Zlin region, therefore, in order to develop and increase the share of GDP per capita in the Zlin region, and should make better use of industrial zones, which are located in this region. It must also improve conditions for business and also make that region to attract investors, and skilled workforce. This reaches the offer of unused industrial zone entrepreneurs will be better informed about how to obtain financial support from EU funds and increase the proportion of the involvement of business in the Zlin region to both existing projects and in preparing projects.

Zlin region must begin to address the above problems, which have a negative impact on the development of the region. Must use all the potential and possibilities, which is to increase the seductiveness of this region for investors and businesses and thus to prevent increased unemployment, in particular, workers who are taught in the field or have completed secondary education and to prevent the departure of skilled workers and university graduates from Zlin region.

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